

Utilisation of Mesh-in-the-Sky and Advanced IoT Sensors in Agriculture

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Abstract—Deploying Internet of Things sensors in remote agricultural areas presents formidable challenges, especially for real-time monitoring of crops, farmland habitats, and livestock farms where traditional communication infrastructure is absent. This paper introduces 'Mesh-in-the-Sky,' an innovative approach utilizing Unmanned Aerial Vehicles as signal nodes in areas lacking cellular and Long-Range coverage. By establishing Unmanned Aerial Vehicles-based communication networks, this method extends connectivity to remote, out-of-coverage zones, significantly enhancing operational efficiency and cost-effectiveness while ensuring robust, secure data transmission through Unmanned Aerial Vehicle links. Comprehensive lab and field trials validate the efficacy of the 'Mesh-in-the-Sky' solution, demonstrating its capability to establish reliable communication beyond line-of-sight constraints using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles-enabled data links.

Index Terms—Wireless communication, drones, UAVs, IoT sensors, Farmland Habitats, Livestock farms, Beyond Line of Sight

I. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural lands in remote locations often remain unattended or require human presence to monitor and maintain their habitats. Such lands are typically situated in areas that lack cellular, Long Range, or any traditional communication

coverage, leading to a lack of awareness regarding the well-being of the farmlands and their habitats, especially during emergencies or unexpected events [1].

Innovative solutions have been developed to address the connectivity challenges in remote agricultural lands. One approach involves deploying LoRa networks that interconnect wireless sensing nodes and create dedicated agricultural networks [2]. However, LoRa networks require cellular or Ethernet connectivity, which may be unavailable in remote areas. To overcome this, UAVs equipped with visual and near-infrared cameras are used to map fields and collect data in isolated locations [3]. Despite their benefits, UAVs struggle with controllability Beyond Line of Sight (BLOS). To address this, some studies propose using UAVs in conjunction with satellites. These UAVs switch from Wi-Fi to satellite communication when beyond the line of sight, ensuring reliable data transmission and control [4]. This approach, though, introduces other drawbacks, such as costly airtime plans and slower connection speeds.

The innovation presented in this article is a solution called "Mesh-in-the-Sky," which leverages RiniMesh Software Defined Radios (SDRs) and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to create a dynamic and flexible communication network. This solution forms a swarm of SDRs, effectively creating a mesh network that can connect BLOS regions. By deploying this system, reliable connectivity is ensured between the deployed IoT sensors in the agricultural fields and the region with

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internet coverage.

This innovative approach allows for seamless data transmission, enhancing the overall communication infrastructure in remote agricultural lands. By ensuring that data from IoT sensors can be reliably transmitted to data aggregation points, farmers and researchers can gain real-time insights and make informed decisions. Furthermore, the flexibility of the "Mesh-in-the-Sky" system means it can be rapidly deployed and adjusted to interconnect various locations, making it a versatile solution for various connectivity challenges in remote areas.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1. Mesh-in-the-Sky UAV-based Communication System

In response to the challenges associated with the complex and diverse pilot scenarios of the NESTLER project, the concept of operations (CONOPS) illustrated in Figure 1 has been developed introducing "Mesh in the Sky", which plays a significant role in developing an integrated crop management system that enables the aggregation of data from multiple environmental IoT sensor nodes [5]. Moreover, the CONOPS system architecture also comprises of three other main elements: the Sensors, the Ground Station (or Data Collector Case), and the Cellular Connectivity routing devices.

A. Sensors

The sensors continuously collect environmental data, such as soil moisture, temperature, humidity, light intensity, and factors affecting crop health [5] [6], as well as crop quality at the end of the production cycle [7]. This data aggregation provides a real-time, detailed view of environmental conditions, enabling data-driven crop quality prediction and tailored agronomic interventions [5].

Field sensors use various communication interfaces, leveraging cellular or LoRa coverage when available [5] [8]. However, to represent diverse agroecological conditions in pilot regions, sensors may be deployed in areas with limited or no cellular or LoRa coverage [9]. For instance, one NESTLER pilot in Nigeria aims to model cassava yield across six distinct

agro-ecological zones, from the Atlantic coast to the Sahel [10]. In remote sites with limited network coverage, the proposed Mesh-in-the-Sky ensures seamless integration with all deployed sensors.

B. Ground Station Case

Seamless integration with deployed sensors is achieved through the proposed Data Collector (DC) or the Ground Station (GS), which will be installed in areas lacking communication infrastructure. The GS will collect data from the sensors and will host a mesh node or a Software Defined Radio (SDR) device called RiniGARD, a Data Aggregator, and a laptop to verify internet connectivity between the regions. Finally, ground stations (GS) could be connected to any Internet Protocol (IP) system, including IEEE802.11xx or LoRa, making integration much easier and communication more reliable.

C. Data Aggregator

Data aggregator is a device designed to support the complete operating cycle of the mesh radio architecture (Figure 2). The Data Aggregator has been designed for typical data receiving and transmitting to the cloud [11]. The receiving end of the device features two communication protocols: a Long-Range Radio Module (LoRa) and a Bluetooth Low Energy Module (BLE), which is embedded in the Infineon CYBLE-416045-02 EZ-BLE Microcontroller Unit (MCU).

The LoRa and BLE communication modules retrieve data from a network of sensors and store this data in the MCU memory. The MCU, apart from storing all the data received by the radio modules, it also prepares the batch of data for transmission to the cloud [12]. The last step of the Data Aggregator involves transmitting the aggregated data from the aggregator to the cloud via the Mesh in the Sky network. The Data Aggregator is configured to send data in JSON format to an MQTT broker via the Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol. Finally, the data is represented on a dashboard using data visualization tools.

Fig. 2. Data Aggregator PCB

D. Mesh Nodes - Software Defined Radio

The Rinimesh Software Defined Radio (SDR), as the main component of the CONOPS architecture, is a device that

handles radio communication and signals via software. More specifically, the software is responsible for handling the modulation and demodulation of radio signals, enabling the transmission and reception of data via predefined communication protocols, including IEEE 802.11xx.

The SDR offers, in a single device, a database of waveforms to meet different customers' needs across a wide range of wireless applications and uses.

The SDRs can also be connected on an ad-hoc basis to form a network that lets each radio automatically connect to other nodes, creating a self-healing, mobile, and dynamic IP mesh network. Each node automatically routes data around the wireless network and can be easily configured to operate without user intervention. This makes the system ideal for harsh environments and rapid deployment scenarios.

Fig. 3. SYLVANUS Mesh in the Sky Radio Node

E. Mesh in the Sky

The Mesh-in-the-Sky is an IP based system, operating using NATO IST 118 standard [13]. This standard is specifically developed for mesh communication in disadvantaged networks where ground infrastructure is poor or not available. It is a broadband mesh supporting up to 100 Mb/s (depending upon the range) but with guaranteed connectivity of 20 Mb/s at UAV ranges of 20 km from the Ground Station (GS). The system architecture is flexible enough to support multiple ground stations distributed upon the area of interest.

The system will support multiple live High Definition(HD) video streams from the drones, proving situation awareness and real time video surveillance which could be used for analytics (detecting early fires, determining size of fires, etc) and any other IoT sensors, plus flight related data (GPS coordinates, control signals, telemetry, etc).

The Mesh-in-the-Sky system architecture allows the installation of various IoT sensors either directly connected on the Drone or can be connected on the Drone via a Ground Station. Connected directly into the Mesh-in-the-Sky, dramatically simplifies the overall networking architecture providing real time sensory data from a wide area of surveillance. However; if the connection into the Mesh-in-the-Sky is not feasible sensors can be connected on the closest Ground Station, from where the aggregated traffic will be transmitted to any control centre via Mesh-in-the-Sky.

III. LABORATORY TRIALS

The initial testing of the proposed Mesh-in-the-Sky architecture has been developed in Rinicom's laboratory. These sections outline the results of these tests and provide more details on the system configuration.

A. System Setup

To conduct the laboratory trials, three Mesh-in-the-Sky nodes illustrated in Figure 4, along with one IP camera, were used. Their MAC and IP addresses are shown in Table I.

Fig. 4. UAV with integrated Mesh in the Sky node during laboratory testing

TABLE I
CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS OF MESH IN THE SKY NODES AND IP CAMERA USED IN LABORATORY TRIALS

RADIO 1	MAC ADDRESS	00:11:6A:03:7F:57
	NODE ID	1
	IP ADDRESS	192.168.1.176
RADIO 2	MAC ADDRESS	00:11:6A:03:7E:C7
	NODE ID	2
	IP ADDRESS	192.168.1.137
RADIO 3	MAC ADDRESS	00:11:6A:03:7F:17
	NODE ID	3
	IP ADDRESS	192.168.1.112
IP Camera	MAC ADDRESS	00:07:5F:C4:25:2E
	NODE ID	MIC IP Starlight 7000i
	IP ADDRESS	192.168.1.165

B. Network Architecture During Laboratory Trials

During the laboratory trials, a scenario where a UAV hovers over the area of a pilot was simulated. This provided connectivity to all ground-based IoT sensors, ground stations (GSs), remote Control Centres (C2), and authorized users. **Figure 5 illustrates the network architecture used for arranging all three mesh nodes, the IP camera, the server, and the network switch, along with the IP address of each device.**

The implementation of the Mesh-in-the-Sky node on a UAV was a trivial task, as a number of constraints needed to be taken into consideration, such as:

- Weight of the node - ensuring that the payload is compliant with UAV take-off characteristics
- Physical dimensions of the node – ensuring that flight dynamics are not affected.
- Power consumption of the node – ensuring that UAV battery is not drained intensively.
- Antenna location of the node – ensuring wide coverage area without unnecessary signal losses.

Fig. 5. MESH Network Architecture During Laboratory Trials

IV. DEMONSTRATION AND CONFIGURATION FROM FIELD TRIALS

The Mesh-in-the-Sky infrastructure (Figure 8) was tested and verified in the field transferring data from field-deployed IoT sensors. IoT communication was integrated with the Wireless Mesh and connected to the Internet via a 5G router, enabling Internet access for the sensors. The wireless mesh reliably transported images and HD videos from the field.

The demonstration had two stages. In stage one, sensors and one SDR on Station A, and Ground Station B shown in Figure 6, were deployed at a distance where the two SDRs could not communicate. This was confirmed via the open-source device management platform as in Figure 7.

Fig. 6. Field-trial - Aggregator/Sensors side

Fig. 7. Device Management Platform - No device found

Proceeding to the Mesh-in-the-Sky part of the field trials, and after acknowledging that there was no communication

between the two stations, a UAV incorporating an SDR, as shown in Figure 8, was launched to establish a connection between the two stations.

Fig. 8. Field-trial - Node on UAV

As shown in Figure 9, during the drone's flight, a link was successfully established between the two stations, as confirmed by the reception of data on the open-source device management platform.

Fig. 9. Device Management Platform - Generated data

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the results obtained during the development, implementation, testing and verification of the Mesh-in-the-Sky secure communication solution integrated with IoT devices and data aggregator are presented. The developed system eliminates the drawbacks of the legacy communication systems and allows seamless integration with both ground-based and on-board IoT sensors.

The system has passed proof-of-concept tests and regulatory validation in the lab. It is currently in testing mode for performance characterization, using a UAV in environments simulating common operational scenarios for Project NESTLER pilots. In conclusion, the developed Mesh-in-the-Sky radio system provided sufficient bandwidth to ensure uninterrupted transmission of HD video streams. Moreover, it fully complies with the requirements and is ready for pilot trials in real-life scenarios.

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